

The RADON Verification Tool: Proofs of Correctness

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Abstract

The *RADON Constraint Definition Language (CDL)* can be used to encode both functional and non-functional requirements on Function as a Service (FaaS) architecture. The primary use of its associated *Verification Tool* is to check whether a given architecture conforms to a given CDL specification. In addition, it can also suggest corrections to a RADON model that does not conform to a CDL specification and learn requirements (expressed as CDL constraints) from examples of valid and invalid RADON models. This document presents the formal semantics for the CDL and the proofs of correctness of the Verification Tool.

1 Introduction

The RADON Constraint Definition Language (CDL) provides a way of expressing the high level functional and non-functional requirements of a FaaS architecture. The associated Verification Tool (VT) has three main modes of execution: (1) Verification; (2) Correction; and (3) Learning. These three modes are detailed below.

1. **Verification.** In this mode (detailed in [Law19]), the tool checks whether a given RADON model complies with the constraints expressed in a given CDL specification.
2. **Correction.** In this mode, the tool searches for a modification of a (non-compliant) RADON model, in order to make it comply with the constraints in a given CDL specification.
3. **Learning.** In this mode, the tool is given examples of valid and invalid RADON models, and a partial CDL specification. The tool then searches for an additional set of CDL constraints, which (when added to the partial CDL specification) rule out all of the invalid examples, while maintaining consistency with the valid examples.

The first version of the CDL was presented in [Law19], together with a preliminary version of the Verification Tool which already had prototype versions of the first two execution modes. An updated version of the CDL and VT have since been presented in [Law20].

The verification mode of the VT works by translating a CDL specification (including a RADON model) into the language of Answer Set Programming (ASP) [GL88, BET11] and using an ASP solver [GKK⁺16] to search for inconsistencies between the RADON model and the requirements defined in the CDL specification. The correction and learning modes of the tool make use of the ILASP (Inductive Learning of Answer Set Programs) system [LRB14, LRB15a, LRB20] for learning ASP programs.

2 Background

In this section we introduce basic notions and terminologies used throughout the paper. Given any atoms $h_1, \dots, h_o, b_1, \dots, b_n, c_1, \dots, c_m$, a *disjunctive rule* is of the form $h_1; \dots; h_o :- b_1, \dots, b_n, \text{not } c_1, \dots, \text{not } c_m$, where $h_1; \dots; h_o$ is the *head* and $b_1, \dots, b_n, \text{not } c_1, \dots, \text{not } c_m$ (collectively) is the *body* of the rule, and “not” represents negation as failure. If $o = 0$, the rule is called a *constraint*, and if $o = 1$, the rule is called a *normal rule*. If $o = 1$ and $m = 0$ then the rule is called a *definite rule*. A variable in a rule is said to be *safe* if it occurs in at least one positive literal (i.e. the b_i ’s in the above rule) in the body of the rule. A program is a set of disjunctive rules. The Herbrand Base of a program P , denoted HB_P , is the set of variable free (ground) atoms that can be formed from predicates and constants in P . The subsets of HB_P are called the (Herbrand) interpretations of P . Given a program P and an Herbrand interpretation $I \subseteq HB_P$, the *reduct* P^I is constructed from the grounding of P in 3 steps: firstly, remove rules whose bodies contain the negation of an atom in I ; secondly, remove all negative literals from the remaining rules; and finally, replace the head of any constraint with \perp (where $\perp \notin HB_P$). Any $I \subseteq HB_P$ is an *answer set* of P if it is a minimal model of the reduct P^I . We denote the set of answer sets of a program P with $AS(P)$. For an introduction to ASP, please see [GK14]. For any atom a we write that $P \models_b a$ (resp. $P \models_c a$) iff a is in at least one (resp. every) answer set of P .

We now present the form of examples used in this paper, which were first formalised in [LRB18b]. A *partial interpretation* e is a pair of sets of ground atoms $\langle e^{inc}, e^{exc} \rangle$; we refer to e^{inc} and e^{exc} as the *inclusions* and *exclusions* respectively. An interpretation I is said to *extend* e iff $e^{inc} \subseteq I$ and $e^{exc} \cap I = \emptyset$. A *context-dependent partial interpretation* (CDPI) is a pair $e = \langle e_{pi}, e_{ctx} \rangle$, where e_{pi} is a partial interpretation and e_{ctx} is an ASP program called a *context*. A CDPI e is *accepted* by a program P if and only if there is an answer set of $P \cup e_{ctx}$ that extends e_{pi} .

The learning mode of the verification tool makes use of the ILASP (Inductive Learning of Answer Set Programs) system [LRB15a]. For more information on ILASP, see the relevant papers [LRB15b, LRB16, LRB18a]. We now recall the definition of a $ILP_{LAS}^{context}$ task (which is a simplified version of the $ILP_{LOAS}^{context}$ task defined in [Law18]).

Definition 2.1. A *Context-dependent Learning from Answer Sets* ($ILP_{LAS}^{context}$) task is a tuple $T = \langle B, S_M, \langle E^+, E^-, O^b, O^c \rangle \rangle$ where B is an ASP program, S_M is a set of ASP rules and E^+ and E^- are finite sets of CDPIs. A hypothesis $H \subseteq S_M$ is an inductive solution of T if and only if:

1. $\forall e \in E^+, B \cup H$ accepts e
2. $\forall e \in E^-, B \cup H$ does not accept e

A hypothesis is said to be an *optimal* inductive solution of a task if it is an inductive solution and there is no shorter inductive solution of the task. This definition depends on a definition of the *length* of the hypothesis, which is usually defined as the number of literals in the hypothesis. In order to allow general notions of length, we slightly modify the notation in this paper, so that S_M is now a set of pairs $\langle \text{length}, R \rangle$, where R is a rule in the hypothesis space and length is the length of R .

3 The Constraint Definition Language (CDL)

3.1 Language

This subsection presents the grammar for the language of the CDL. Note that in places, this is a subset of the full CDL presented in [Law19]. The omitted features are syntactic sugar; for example, the condition $A \Rightarrow B$ can be rewritten as $\text{NOT } A \text{ OR } B$. For more a more detailed explanation of the full language of the CDL, please see [Law19].

3.1.1 Primitives

```
word -> [a-zA-Z][a-zA-Z0-9_\-]*
variable -> $[a-zA-Z][a-zA-Z0-9_]*
string -> '"' [^"]* '"'
number -> sign integer decimal
```

```
sign ->
sign -> '-'
```

```
integer -> [0-9]
integer -> [1-9] [0-9]+
```

```
decimal ->
decimal -> '.' [0-9]+
```

3.1.2 Entities and Values

```
value -> number | variable | string |
        entity | set | array | condition | arithmetic_expression
value -> set '.' 'size'
value -> array '[' value ']'
value -> array '.' 'size'
value -> '(' value binop value ')'
```

```
binop -> '+' | '-' | '*' | '/'
```

```
entity -> word | variable
entity -> entity '.' word
```

```
set -> '{' '}'
set -> entity
set -> '{' list_of_elements '}'
set -> set '.' 'such_that' '(' condition ')
set -> set '.' 'union' '(' set ')
set -> set '.' 'intersection' '(' set ')
set -> set '.' 'subtract' '(' set ')
set -> 'closure' '(' set ',' variable ',' variable ':' set ',' condition ')'
```

```
list_of_elements -> value
list_of_elements -> value ',' list_of_elements
```

```

array -> '[' ']'
array -> '[' list_of_elements ']'

condition -> '(' value comparison value ')'
condition -> set '.' 'includes' '(' value ')'
condition -> set '.' 'empty' '(' ')'
condition -> set '.' 'subset' '(' set ')'
condition -> 'NOT' condition
condition -> condition 'AND' condition
condition -> condition 'OR' condition
condition -> quantifier '(' variable ':' entity ',' condition ')'
condition -> entity '.' satisfies '(' condition_extra ')'
condition -> entity '.' consistent
condition -> entity '.' inconsistent

comparison -> '=' | '!=' | '<' | '<=' | '>' | '>='

quantifier -> 'FORALL' | 'EXISTS'

```

3.1.3 Specifications

```

statement -> entity '=' value
statement -> 'ASSERT' '(' condition ')'
statement -> 'timeline' entity '[' value ']' ';'

cdl_specification ->
cdl_specification -> statement ';' cdl_specification

```

3.2 Assumptions

Note that the definition of sets in the general specification of the CDL in the previous subsection allows for abstractly defined sets over an infinite domain. In order to make the verification tool computationally feasible, we introduce a restricted type of set. General sets can still be defined, and have their uses, but the restricted *explicitly defined* sets are the only ones which are allowed to be used in quantified conditions.

Definition 3.1. Let S be a CDL specification. A value v in S is an explicitly defined set if one of the following holds:

- v is of the form $\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$; or
- v is of the form $\{a..b\}$, where a and b are integers¹; or
- There is a statement of the form $(v = s) \in S$, where s is an explicitly defined set; or
- v is of the form $s_1.\text{subtract}(s_2)$, where s_1 and s_2 are both explicitly defined sets; or
- v is of the form $s_1.\text{union}(s_2)$, where s_1 and s_2 are both explicitly defined sets; or

¹In fact, the implementation is slightly more general, allowing a and b to be entities which are equal to integers.

- v is of the form $s_1.\text{intersection}(s_2)$, where s_1 and s_2 are both explicitly defined sets; or
- v is of the form $s.\text{such_that}(\text{var}, c)$, where s is an explicitly defined set, v is a variable and c is a CDL-condition; or
- v is of the form $\text{closure}(s_1, \text{var}_1, \text{var}_2 : s_2, c)$, where s_1 and s_2 are explicitly defined sets, var_1 and var_2 are variables and c is a CDL-condition.

Nothing else is an explicitly defined set.

Definition 3.2. Let S be a CDL specification, e be an entity and let $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$. e is *reachable at depth n* iff at least one of the following holds:

- There is a CDL statement containing e .
- e is of the form $e'.\text{property}$ where e' is reachable at depth $n - 1$.
- e is of the form $e'.\text{property}(e_1, \dots, e_n)$ where e' and e_1, \dots, e_n are all reachable at depth $n - 1$.
- e is of the form $e_1[e_2]$ where e_1 and e_2 are both reachable at depth $n - 1$.

Nothing else is reachable at depth n .

For the rest of this document, we assume that every entity is reachable at some pre-defined maximum depth n (in the implementation of the verification tool, by default this is 2, but it can be increased by the user).

As closure operators are only defined as explicit sets, they can be rewritten using the `such_that` operator. For example, given a closure operator defined over a set `domain_set` containing n arguments, we can rewrite the following statement:

```
closure_set = closure(initial_set, $ACC, $V2 : domain_set, condition);
```

The above statement can be rewritten as:

```
closure_set_i[1] = initial_set;
ASSERT(FORALL($i : {1..n},
  (closure_set_i[$i + 1] = domain_set.such_that($V2,
    condition[$ACC \ closure_set_i[$i]]) .union(closure_set_i[$i])
  )
));
closure_set = closure_set_i[n + 1];
```

Note that as the domain contains n elements, at most n applications are needed, which is why this rewrite is guaranteed to work. For the rest of this document, we assume that all closure operations have been rewritten in this way.

Similarly, the intersection and subtraction operators can be written in terms of `such_that`, so we assume they have been rewritten.

In addition to conforming to the grammar so far, CDL statements must not contain any variable which is not bound to a quantifier (i.e. no variable can occur outside of a `FORALL` or `EXISTS` where it is the variable before the `'.'`). For example, `ASSERT(FORALL($X : s, $X > 0 AND $X < 20))` is a valid CDL statement, but `ASSERT($X > 0 AND FORALL($X : s, $X < 20))` is invalid, as the first `$X` is not bound to a quantifier.

3.3 Semantics

Definition 3.3. A *CDL-interpretation* I consists of a set of CDL conditions. A CDL-interpretation I' is said to be an *extension* of I if and only if $I \subseteq I'$.

Definition 3.4. Let S be a CDL specification. A CDL-interpretation I is said to be *complete* iff each of the following properties holds:

1. For each v that is reachable at depth n , $(v = v) \in I$.
2. For each $(v1 = v2) \in I$, $(v2 = v1) \in I$.
3. For each pair $(v1 = v2)$ and $(v2 = v3) \in I$, $(v1 = v3) \in I$.
4. For each pair $(v1 = v2)$ and $(v2.property = v3) \in I$ such that $v1.property$ is reachable at depth n , $(v1.property = v3) \in I$.
5. For each $(NOT (v1 = v2)) \in I$, $(v1 \neq v2) \in I$.
6. For each $(NOT (v1 \neq v2)) \in I$, $(v1 = v2) \in I$.
7. For each $(NOT (v1 < v2)) \in I$, $(v1 \geq v2) \in I$.
8. For each $(NOT (v1 \leq v2)) \in I$, $(v1 > v2) \in I$.
9. For each $(NOT (v1 > v2)) \in I$, $(v1 \leq v2) \in I$.
10. For each $(NOT (v1 \geq v2)) \in I$, $(v1 < v2) \in I$.
11. For each expression e in the language such that e evaluates to v , $(e = v) \in I$. For instance, if $(e = t + 2) \in I$ and $(t = 1) \in I$, $(e = 3) \in I$. This is similarly defined for all set operations (`size`, `such_that` and `union`) over explicitly defined sets.
12. For any v reachable at depth n such that $(v = S_1.such_that(\$X, C)) \in I$, for each $S_1.includes(v_2) \in I$ either $(NOT v.includes(v_2)) \in I$ and $(NOT C[\$X \setminus v_2]) \in I$ or $v.includes(v_2) \in I$ and $C[\$X \setminus v_2] \in I$. Furthermore, for each $v.includes(v_2) \in I$, $C[\$X \setminus v_2] \in I$ and $S_1.includes(v_2) \in I$.
13. For any v reachable at depth n such that $(v = S_1.union(S_2)) \in I$, for each v_2 that is reachable at depth n : (1) $v.includes(v_2) \in I$ if and only if $S_1.includes(v_2) \in I$ and $S_2.includes(v_2) \in I$; and (2) $(NOT v.includes(v_2)) \in I$ if and only if $(NOT S_1.includes(v_2)) \in I$ and $(NOT S_2.includes(v_2)) \in I$.
14. For each $(C1 AND C2) \in I$, $C1 \in I$ and $C2 \in I$.
15. For each $(C1 OR C2) \in I$, either $C1 \in I$ or $C2 \in I$.
16. For each $(FORALL(V : S, C)) \in I$, such that s is an explicitly defined set, for each e such that $(s.includes(e) \in I, C[V \setminus e] \in I$, where $C[V \setminus e]$ is constructed by replacing all occurrences of V in C with e .

17. For each $(\text{EXISTS}(V : S, C)) \in I$, such that s is an explicitly defined set, either there is at least one e such that $(s.\text{includes}(e)) \in I$ and $C[V \setminus e] \in I$ or $\perp \in I$.
18. For each $(\text{NOT}(C1 \text{ AND } C2)) \in I$, either $(\text{NOT } C1) \in I$ or $(\text{NOT } C2) \in I$.
19. For each $(\text{NOT}(C1 \text{ OR } C2)) \in I$, $(\text{NOT } C1) \in I$ and $(\text{NOT } C2) \in I$.
20. For each $(\text{NOT FORALL}(V : S, C)) \in I$, such that s is an explicitly defined set, either there is at least one e such that $(s.\text{includes}(e)) \in I$ and $\text{NOT } C[V \setminus e] \in I$ or $\perp \in I$.
21. For each $(\text{NOT EXISTS}(V : S, C)) \in I$, such that s is an explicitly defined set, for each e such that $(s.\text{includes}(e)) \in I$, $\text{NOT } C[V \setminus e] \in I$, where $C[V \setminus e]$ is constructed by replacing all occurrences of V in C with e .
22. For each $(\text{NOT}(\text{NOT } C)) \in I$, $C \in I$.
23. For each $(S.\text{empty}()) \in I$, $(S = \emptyset) \in I$.
24. For each $(\text{NOT } S.\text{empty}()) \in I$, $(S \neq \emptyset) \in I$.
25. For each $(S.\text{includes}(E)) \in I$, such that $(S = \{s_1, \dots, s_n\}) \in I$, either $(s_i = E) \in I$ for at least one $i \in [1, n]$, or $\perp \in I$.
26. For each $(\text{NOT } S.\text{includes}(E)) \in I$, such that $(S = \{s_1, \dots, s_n\}) \in I$, $(s_i \neq E) \in I$ for each $i \in [1, n]$.
27. For each $(S1.\text{subset}(S2)) \in I$, for each $(S1.\text{includes}(E)) \in I$, $(S2.\text{includes}(E)) \in I$.
28. For each $(\text{NOT } S1.\text{subset}(S2)) \in I$, $(S1.\text{includes}(\text{skolem}_-(S1, S2))) \in I$ and $(\text{NOT } S2.\text{includes}(\text{skolem}_-(S1, S2))) \in I$ (where skolem_- is a reserved keyword).
29. For each $(S1.\text{subset}(S2)) \in I$ such that $(S1 = \{s_1, \dots, s_n\}) \in I$, for each $i \in [1, n]$, $(S2.\text{includes}(s_i)) \in I$.
30. For each $(\text{NOT } S1.\text{subset}(S2)) \in I$ such that $(S1 = \{s_1, \dots, s_n\}) \in I$, either there is at least one $i \in [1, n]$ s.t. $(\text{NOT } S2.\text{includes}(s_i)) \in I$ or $\perp \in I$.

Definition 3.5. A CDL-interpretation I is said to be consistent iff each of the following properties holds:

1. There is no pair $(v_1 = v_2)$ and $(v_1 = v_3) \in I$ such that v_2 and v_3 are two distinct value types.
2. There is no pair $(v_1 = v_2)$ and $(v_1 \neq v_2) \in I$.
3. There is no $C \in I$ such that $(\text{NOT } C) \in I$.
4. There is a total preorder \preceq over the entities referred to in I s.t. the following all hold:
 - (a) For any two entities e_1 and e_2 s.t. $(e_1 < e_2) \in I$, $e_1 \preceq e_2$ and $e_1 \not\preceq e_2$.
 - (b) For any two entities e_1 and e_2 s.t. $(e_1 \leq e_2) \in I$, $e_1 \preceq e_2$.
 - (c) For any two entities e_1 and e_2 s.t. $(e_1 > e_2) \in I$, $e_2 \preceq e_1$ and $e_2 \not\preceq e_1$.

- (d) For any two entities e_1 and e_2 s.t. $(e_1 \geq e_2) \in I$, $e_2 \preceq e_1$.
 - (e) For any two entities e_1 and e_2 s.t. $(e_1 = e_2) \in I$, $e_1 \preceq e_2$ and $e_2 \preceq e_1$.
 - (f) For any two entities e_1 and e_2 s.t. $(e_1 \neq e_2) \in I$, either $e_1 \preceq e_2$ or $e_2 \preceq e_1$ (but not both).
5. $\perp \notin I$.

Definition 3.6. A CDL-interpretation I is said to satisfy a set of CDL statements S if and only if each of the following statements holds:

1. For each statement $(v_1 = v_2) \in S$, $(v_1 = v_2) \in I$.
2. For each statement $(\text{ASSERT}(C)) \in S$, $C \in I$.

Definition 3.7. A CDL-interpretation is said to be a CDL-model of a set of CDL statements S if and only if it is complete and consistent and it satisfies S .

We now define the semantics of CDL-specifications which include timelines.

Definition 3.8. Let S be a CDL specification. The time points of S are of the form $\text{tl}[i]$, where $(\text{timeline } \text{tl}[n]) \in S$ and $i \in [1, n]$.

Definition 3.9. Let S be a set of CDL statements and let I_{base} be a CDL-model of S . For each time point tp , $S[\text{tp}]$ is the CDL-interpretation containing the following:

1. The condition C for each $\text{tp.satisfies}(C) \in I_{\text{base}}$.
2. The condition $(e_1 = e_2)$ for each $(e_1 = e_2) \in I_{\text{base}}$.

A *temporal CDL-model* is a pair $\mathcal{T} = \langle I_{\text{base}}, TM \rangle$ such that:

1. I_{base} is a CDL-model of S .
2. For each time point tp for which $\text{tp.consistent}() \in I_{\text{base}}$, $\langle \text{tp}, I_{\text{tp}} \rangle \in TM$ and I_{tp} is a CDL-model of $S[\text{tp}]$.
3. For each time point tp for which $\text{tp.consistent}() \in I_{\text{base}}$, for each $(e_1 = e_2) \in I_{\text{tp}}$, $(e_1 = e_2) \in I_{\text{base}}$.
4. The equality conditions in the consistent CDL-models in \mathcal{T} are minimal (i.e. there is no \mathcal{T}' satisfying (1)-(3) with a smaller set of equality conditions).
5. For each time point tp for which $\text{tp.inconsistent}() \in I_{\text{base}}$, $S[\text{tp}]$ has no CDL-models.

In addition to the main specification, CDL tasks contain *inconsistency specifications*, which are further sets of CDL-statements.

Definition 3.10. Let S be a CDL specification and Inc be an inconsistency specification (i.e. another CDL specification). Inc is *violated* by S if $S \cup Inc$ has at least one temporal CDL-model.

4 The ASP Representations used by the Tool

We now present a translation from the CDL to ASP. Note that this is very similar to the encoding used by the verification tool, but has been simplified in places. The actual encoding used by the verification tool is more complicated in places to reduce the size of the grounding of the ASP program (and thus reduce the computation time). Some predicates are also named differently (names have been changed in this document for better clarity).

4.1 Representing the search for CDL-models in ASP

Definition 4.1. For any value v occurring anywhere in S , $\mathcal{M}_{term}(v)$ denotes the term $entity_{-}(v_{id}, V_1, \dots, V_n)$, where V_1, \dots, V_n are the variables which occur freely in v and v_{id} is a constant that is unique to v .

Definition 4.2. For any value v occurring anywhere in S , we define $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(v)$ as follows:

1. If v is of the form $(C_1 \text{ OR } C_2)$, $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
 - (a) $holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(C_1)); holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(C_2)) :- holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v))$.
 - (b) $n_holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(C_1)) :- n_holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v))$.
 - (c) $n_holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(C_2)) :- n_holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v))$.
 - (d) $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(C_1)$
 - (e) $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(C_2)$
2. If v is of the form $(C_1 \text{ AND } C_2)$, $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
 - (a) $holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(C_1)) :- holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v))$.
 - (b) $holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(C_2)) :- holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v))$.
 - (c) $n_holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(C_1)); n_holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(C_2)) :- n_holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v))$.
 - (d) $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(C_1)$
 - (e) $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(C_2)$
3. If v is of the form $(\text{NOT } C)$, $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
 - (a) $n_holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(C)) :- holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v))$.
 - (b) $holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(C)) :- n_holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v))$.
 - (c) $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(C)$
4. If v is of the form $\text{FORALL}(\text{Var} : S, C)$, $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
 - (a) $holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(C)) :- holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v)), in(S, \text{Var})$.
 - (b) $holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(\perp)); n_holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(C)) : in(S, \text{Var}) :- n_holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v))$.
 - (c) $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(C)$
 - (d) $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(S)$

5. If v is of the form $\text{EXISTS}(\text{Var} : \text{S}, \text{C})$, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
- (a) $\text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\perp); \text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{C})) : \text{in}(\text{S}, \text{Var}) : - \text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v))).$
 - (b) $\text{n_holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{C})) : - \text{n_holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)), \text{in}(\text{S}, \text{Var}).$
 - (c) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(\text{C})$
 - (d) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(\text{S})$
6. If v is of the form $\text{s}_1.\text{union}(\text{s}_2)$, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
- (a) $\text{holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_1), \text{includes}, \text{Var})); \text{holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_2), \text{includes}, \text{Var})) : - \text{holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v), \text{includes}, \text{Var})).$
 - (b) $\text{n_holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_1), \text{includes}, \text{Var})) : - \text{n_holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v), \text{includes}, \text{Var})).$
 - (c) $\text{n_holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_2), \text{includes}, \text{Var})) : - \text{n_holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v), \text{includes}, \text{Var})).$
 - (d) $\text{explicit_set}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)) : - \text{explicit_set}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_1)), \text{explicit_set}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_2)).$
 - (e) $\text{in}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v), \text{E}) : - \text{in}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_1), \text{E}).$
 - (f) $\text{in}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v), \text{E}) : - \text{in}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_2), \text{E}).$
 - (g) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(\text{s}_1)$
 - (h) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(\text{s}_2)$
7. If v is of the form $\text{s}.\text{such_that}(\text{Var}, \text{C})$, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
- (a) $\text{holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}), \text{includes}, \text{Var})) : - \text{holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v), \text{includes}, \text{Var})).$
 - (b) $\text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{C})) : - \text{holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v), \text{includes}, \text{Var})).$
 - (c) $\text{n_holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}), \text{includes}, \text{Var})); \text{n_holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{C})) : - \text{holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v), \text{includes}, \text{Var})).$
 - (d) $\text{explicit_set}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)) : - \text{explicit_set}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s})).$
 - (e) $\text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{C})); \text{n_holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{C})) : - \text{in}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s})).$
 - (f) $\text{in}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v), \text{Var}); \text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{C})) : - \text{in}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}), \text{Var}).$
 - (g) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(\text{s})$
 - (h) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(\text{C})$
8. If v is of the form $\text{s}_1.\text{subset}(\text{s}_2)$, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
- (a) $\text{holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_2), \text{includes}, \text{Var})) : - \text{holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_1), \text{includes}, \text{Var})), \text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
 - (b) $\text{holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_1), \text{includes}, \text{skolem_}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_1, \text{s}_2)))) : - \text{n_holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
 - (c) $\text{n_holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_1), \text{includes}, \text{skolem_}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_1, \text{s}_2)))) : - \text{n_holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
 - (d) $\text{holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_2), \text{includes}, \text{Var})) : - \text{in}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_1), \text{Var}), \text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
 - (e) $\text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\perp)); \text{n_holds}(\text{fn}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_2), \text{includes}, \text{Var})) : \text{in}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\text{s}_1), \text{Var}) : - \text{n_holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$

- (f) $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(s_1)$
 - (g) $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(s_2)$
9. If v is of the form $s.empty()$, $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
- (a) $holds(fn(\mathcal{M}_{term}(s), empty)) :- holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v)).$
 - (b) $n_holds(fn(\mathcal{M}_{term}(s), empty)) :- n_holds(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v)).$
 - (c) $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(s)$
10. If v is of the form $arr_expr[index_expr]$, $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
- (a) $eq(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v), arr(Arr, (at, Index))) :-$
 $eq(\mathcal{M}_{term}(arr_expr), Arr), eq(\mathcal{M}_{term}(index_expr), Index),$
 $depth(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v), N), N \leq n.$
 - (b) $depth(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v), N2 + 1) :-$
 $depth(\mathcal{M}_{term}(arr_expr), N1), depth(\mathcal{M}_{term}(index_expr), N2), N1 < N2, N2 < n.$
 - (c) $depth(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v), N1 + 1) :-$
 $depth(\mathcal{M}_{term}(arr_expr), N1), depth(\mathcal{M}_{term}(index_expr), N2), N1 \geq N2, N1 < n.$
 - (d) $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(arr_expr)$
 - (e) $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(index_expr)$
11. If v is of the form $\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$, $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
- (a) $in(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v), e_i).$ for each $i \in [1, n]$
 - (b) $explicit_set(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v)).$
 - (c) $eq(fn(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v), size), n).$
 - (d) $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(e_i)$ for each $i \in [1, n]$
12. If v is of the form $\{e_1..e_2\}$ (where e_1 and e_2 are both integers²), $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
- (a) $in(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v), i).$ for each $i \in [e_1, e_2]$
 - (b) $explicit_set(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v)).$
 - (c) $eq(fn(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v), size), e_2 - e_1).$
13. If v is of the form $e_1 \text{ op } e_2$ (where $op \in \{+, -, *, /\}$), $\mathcal{M}_{translation}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
- (a) $eq(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v), Val1 \text{ op } Val2) :-$
 $eq(\mathcal{M}_{term}(e_1), Val1), eq(\mathcal{M}_{term}(e_2), Val2)$
 $|Val1 \text{ op } Val2| \leq integer_bound, \quad depth(\mathcal{M}_{term}(v), N), N \leq n.$

²This is a slight simplification – the implementation of the verification tool also permits e_1 and e_2 to be entities which evaluate to integers.

- (b) $\text{depth}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v), N2 + 1) :-$
 $\text{depth}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1), N1), \text{depth}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2), N2), N1 < N2, N2 < n.$
 - (c) $\text{depth}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v), N1 + 1) :-$
 $\text{depth}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1), N1), \text{depth}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2), N2), N1 \geq N2, N1 < n.$
 - (d) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_1)$
 - (e) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_2)$
14. If v is of the form $e_1 = e_2$, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
- (a) $\text{eq}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2)) :- \text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
 - (b) $\text{neq}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2)) :- \text{n_holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
 - (c) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_1)$
 - (d) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_2)$
15. If v is of the form $e_1 \neq e_2$, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
- (a) $\text{neq}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2)) :- \text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
 - (b) $\text{eq}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2)) :- \text{n_holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
 - (c) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_1)$
 - (d) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_2)$
16. If v is of the form $e_1 < e_2$, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
- (a) $\text{lt}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2)) :- \text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
 - (b) $\text{lt}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1)); \text{eq}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2)) :- \text{n_holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
 - (c) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_1)$
 - (d) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_2)$
17. If v is of the form $e_1 > e_2$, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
- (a) $\text{lt}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1)) :- \text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
 - (b) $\text{lt}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2)); \text{eq}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2)) :- \text{n_holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
 - (c) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_1)$
 - (d) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_2)$
18. If v is of the form $e_1 \leq e_2$, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
- (a) $\text{lt}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2)); \text{eq}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2)) :- \text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
 - (b) $\text{lt}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1)) :- \text{n_holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
 - (c) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_1)$
 - (d) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_2)$
19. If v is of the form $e_1 \geq e_2$, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(v)$ is the program containing the following:

- (a) $\text{lt}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1)); \text{eq}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2)) :- \text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
- (b) $\text{lt}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2)) :- \text{n_holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
- (c) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_1)$
- (d) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_2)$
20. If v is of the form $e.\text{property}$, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
- (a) $\text{eq}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v), \text{fn}(E, \text{property})) :- \text{eq}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e), E), \text{depth}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v), N), N \leq n.$
- (b) $\text{depth}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v), N + 1) :- \text{depth}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e), N), N < n.$
- (c) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e)$
21. If v is of the form $e_1.\text{includes}(e_2)$, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
- (a) $\text{holds}(\text{fn}(e_1, \text{includes}, e_2)) :- \text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
- (b) $\text{n_holds}(\text{fn}(e_1, \text{includes}, e_2)) :- \text{n_holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
- (c) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_1)$
- (d) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_2)$
22. If v is of the form $e_1.\text{satisfies}(e_2)$, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(v)$ is the program containing the following:
- (a) $\text{holds}(\text{fn}(e_1, \text{satisfies}, e_2)) :- \text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)).$
- (b) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_1)$
- (c) $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_2)$

For all other values v , $\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)$ is empty.

Definition 4.3. For any statement s , we define $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(s)$ as follows:

- If s is of the form $e_1 = e_2$, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(s) = \{\text{equal}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2))\} \cup \mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_1) \cup \mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_2).$
- If s is of the form $\text{ASSERT}(C)$, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(s) = \{\text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(C))\} \cup \mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(C).$
- If s is of the form $\text{timeline } e_1[e_2]$, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(s) = \{\text{equal}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1.\text{size}), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_2))\} \cup \{\text{timeline}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e_1))\} \cup \mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_1.\text{size}) \cup \mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(e_2).$

In addition to the specification specific rules defined above, the representation also contains some general rules, Π , which are below. The value predicate is defined as those entities which are either integers or strings.

$\text{eq}(X, Y) :- \text{eq}(Y, X).$
 $\text{eq}(X, Y) :- \text{eq}(X, Z), \text{eq}(Z, Y).$
 $\text{explicit_set}(X) :- \text{explicit_set}(Y), \text{eq}(X, Y).$

$\perp :- \text{eq}(X, Y), \text{eq}(X, Z), \text{value}(Y), \text{value}(Z), Y \neq Z.$
 $\perp :- \text{eq}(X, Y), \text{eq}(X, Z), \text{explicit_set}(Y), \text{value}(Z), Y \neq Z.$
 $\perp :- \text{eq}(X, Y), \text{neq}(X, Y).$
 $\perp :- \text{holds}(C), \text{n_holds}(C).$
 $\perp :- \text{lt}(X, Y), \text{eq}(X, Y).$
 $\perp :- \text{lt}(X, Y), \text{lt}(Y, X).$
 $\text{lt}(X, Z) :- \text{lt}(X, Y), \text{lt}(Y, Z).$
 $\text{lt}(X, Z) :- \text{lt}(X, Y), \text{eq}(Y, Z).$
 $\text{lt}(X, Z) :- \text{eq}(X, Y), \text{lt}(Y, Z).$

Definition 4.4. Let S be a CDL specification. The ASP program Π_S consists of the following:

- $\text{eq}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e)).$ for each entity in S with no free variables.
- $\text{depth}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e), 0).$ for each entity in S with no free variables.
- $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(s)$ for each $s \in S$.
- Π

Theorem 4.1. Let S be any CDL specification. Π_S has at least one answer set that does not contain \perp if and only if S has at least one CDL-model.

Proof.

- Assume there is at least one CDL-model M_{CDL} of S . We must show that there is at least one answer set of Π_S that does not contain \perp . As there is no negation as failure in Π_S , this is the case if there is at least one model of the program. We can construct a model M_{ASP} from M_{CDL} .

First, let M_{CDL}^* be an extension of M_{CDL} such that M_{CDL}^* is also a CDL-model of S and that there is no larger extension of M_{CDL} that is also a CDL-model. We define M_{ASP}^{Core} as follows:

- $\text{eq}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v_1), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v_2)),$ for each $(v_1 = v_2) \in M_{CDL}^*.$
- $\text{neq}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v_1), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v_2)),$ for each $(v_1 \neq v_2) \in M_{CDL}^*.$
- $\text{lt}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v_1), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v_2)),$ for each $(v_1 < v_2) \in M_{CDL}^*.$
- $\text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(C)),$ for each $C \in M_{CDL}^*.$
- $\text{n_holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(C)),$ for each NOT $C \in M_{CDL}^*.$
- $\text{in}(s, e_i),$ for each $(s = \{e_1, \dots, e_i, \dots, e_n\}) \in M_{CDL}^*.$
- $\text{explicit_set}(s),$ for each $(s = \{e_1, \dots, e_n\}) \in M_{CDL}^*.$
- $\text{eq}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e), \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e))$ for each entity in S with no free variables.

- $\text{depth}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(e), 0)$ for each entity in S with no free variables.

We define M_{ASP} as the least fix-point of the T_P operator applied on M_{ASP}^{Core} , where P is the program containing all rules for `depth`, `explicit_set` and `in`.

In order to show that M_{ASP} is a model of Π_S , we must show that every rule in $\Pi_S \setminus P$ is satisfied (the rules in P are satisfied due to the application of the T_P operator). The first two points in Definition 4.4 are trivially satisfied, so it remains to show the final two.

- Assume there is an $s \in S$ such that M_{ASP} is not a model of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(s)$. Then there must be at least one sub-expression s' of s (i.e. a value used in s) such that for all sub-expressions s'' of s' , M_{ASP} is a model of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(s'')$ but M_{ASP} is not a model of $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(s')$. Hence, for at least one of the rules R in Definition 4.2 (which is not $\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(s'')$ for a sub-expression s'' of s' and is not contained in P), M_{ASP} is not a model of one of the ground instances of R . This cannot be the case, or M_{CDL} would not be complete, as each of the rules is a direct translation of one of the consequences of the definition of CDL-interpretation completeness and satisfaction.
- Π : The two rules in Π that are not in P are direct translations of Points 2 and 3, so must hold as M_{CDL} is a complete CDL-interpretation.

Hence, M_{ASP} is a model of Π_S , meaning Π_S must have at least one answer set.

- Assume there is at least one answer set M_{ASP} of Π_S that does not contain \perp . We must show that there is at least one CDL-model of S . We can construct a model M_{CDL} from M_{ASP} as follows:

Let M_{CDL} be the CDL-interpretation containing:

- $(v = v)$, for each v that is reachable at depth n .
- $(v_1 = v_2)$, for each $\text{eq}(v_1, v_2) \in M_{ASP}$.
- $(v_1 = \{s_1, \dots, s_n\})$, for each $\text{eq}(v_1, v_2) \in M_{ASP}$ such that $\text{explicit_set}(v_2) \in M_{ASP}$ and the s_i 's are the entities for which $\text{in}(v_2, s_i) \in M_{ASP}$.
- $(v_1 < v_2)$, for each $\text{lt}(v_1, v_2) \in M_{ASP}$.
- $(v_1 > v_2)$, for each $\text{lt}(v_2, v_1) \in M_{ASP}$.
- $(v_1 \leq v_2)$, for each $\text{lt}(v_1, v_2) \in M_{ASP}$ and each $\text{eq}(v_1, v_2) \in M_{ASP}$.
- $(v_1 \geq v_2)$, for each $\text{gt}(v_1, v_2) \in M_{ASP}$ and each $\text{eq}(v_1, v_2) \in M_{ASP}$.
- $(v_1 \neq v_2)$, for each $\text{neq}(v_1, v_2) \in M_{ASP}$.
- v , for each $e \in M_{ASP}$ such that $e = \mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(v)$ for some v .

We must show that M_{CDL} is complete, consistent and satisfies S .

- (*completeness*). For M_{CDL} to be complete, it must satisfy each of the points in Definition 3.4. Below, we explain why this is the case for each point in turn.
 - * Point 1. This must be satisfied due to the first point defining M_{CDL} .
 - * Point 2. This is guaranteed by the first rule in Π .

- * Point 3. This is guaranteed by the second rule in Π .
 - * Point 4. This is guaranteed by the rules in Point 20 of Definition 4.2
 - * Point 5. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 14(b) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 6. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 15(b) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 7. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 16(b) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 8. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 18(b) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 9. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 17(b) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 10. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 19(b) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 11. For arithmetic expressions, this is guaranteed by the rules in Point 13 of Definition 4.2. For set operations, the third rule of Π combined with the rules for `explicit_set` ensure that all explicit sets are represented as such in M_{ASP} . The rules in Points 6 and 7 ensure that the elements of these sets are correctly defined.
 - * Point 12. This is guaranteed by the rules in Point 7 of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 13. This is guaranteed by the rules in Point 6 of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 14. This is guaranteed by the rules in Points 2(a) and (b) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 15. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 1(a) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 16. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 4(a) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 17. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 5(a) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 18. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 2(a) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 19. This is guaranteed by the rules in Point 1(b) and (c) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 20. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 4(b) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 21. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 5(b) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 22. This is guaranteed by the rules in Point 3 of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 23. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 9(a) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 24. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 9(b) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 25. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 21(a) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 26. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 21(b) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 27. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 8(a) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 28. This is guaranteed by the rule in Points 8(b) and (c) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 29. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 8(d) of Definition 4.2.
 - * Point 30. This is guaranteed by the rule in Point 8(e) of Definition 4.2.
- (*consistency*). We must show that each of the Points (1-5) in Definition 3.5 are satisfied by M_{CDL} . In fact, all of these are guaranteed by the rules defining \perp and $\perp\tau$ in Π (and the fact that $\perp \notin M_{ASP}$).
 - (*satisfaction*). We must show that the two Points in Definition 3.6 are satisfied by M_{CDL} . These are guaranteed by Points 1 and 2 of Definition 4.3.

□

4.2 Verifying inconsistency of CDL-interpretations

In order to correctly represent time points that should be inconsistent, we need to be able to prove that all extensions of a CDL interpretation are inconsistent.

Lemma 4.2. Let P be a disjunctive logic program with no negation as failure and \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} be new ground atoms. Let $P_{unsat(a,b)}$ be the program consisting of:

- P
 - $\mathbf{h}_i : -\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}_i, \text{body}$ for each disjunctive rule $\mathbf{h}_1 : \mathbf{c}_1; \dots; \mathbf{h}_n : \mathbf{c}_n : -\text{body}$ in P and for each $i \in [1, n]$.
1. $P_{unsat(a,b)} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\} \models_b \mathbf{a}$ if and only if $P_{unsat(a,b)} \models_c \mathbf{a}$.
 2. $AS(P_{unsat(a,b)}) = AS(P)$.

Proof.

1.
 - (Proof that $P_{unsat(a,b)} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\} \models_b \mathbf{a} \Rightarrow P \models_c \mathbf{a}$). Assume that $P_{unsat(a,b)} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\} \models_b \mathbf{a}$ and assume for contradiction that $P \not\models_c \mathbf{a}$. There must be at least one answer set A of P that does not contain \mathbf{a} and at least one answer set A' of $P_{unsat(a,b)} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\}$ that does contain \mathbf{a} . Due to the extra rules in $P_{unsat(a,b)} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\}$, A must be a subset of A' . But A must also be a model of $P_{unsat(a,b)} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\}$, meaning that A' cannot be a minimal model of $P_{unsat(a,b)} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\}$. Hence (as $P_{unsat(a,b)} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\} = (P_{unsat(a,b)} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\})^{A'}$), A' cannot be an answer set of $P_{unsat(a,b)} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\}$, which contradicts the initial assumption.
 - (Proof that $P_{unsat(a,b)} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\} \models_b \mathbf{a} \Leftarrow P \models_c \mathbf{a}$). Assume that $P \models_c \mathbf{a}$ and assume for contradiction that $P_{unsat(a,b)} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\} \not\models_b \mathbf{a}$. As $P_{unsat(a,b)} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\}$ has no negation as failure, there must be at least one answer set A of $P_{unsat(a,b)} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\}$, (this A does not contain \mathbf{a}). As A does not contain \mathbf{a} , the extra rules in $P_{unsat(a,b)} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\}$ are irrelevant (other than the fact \mathbf{b}). Hence, $A \setminus \{\mathbf{b}\}$ must be a minimal model of P . Therefore, $A \setminus \{\mathbf{b}\}$ is an answer set of P , meaning that P cannot cautiously entail \mathbf{a} . This contradicts the initial assumption.
2. No minimal model of $P_{unsat(a,b)}$ can contain \mathbf{b} . This means that the extra rules in $P_{unsat(a,b)}$ are irrelevant, meaning that the minimal models of $P_{unsat(a,b)}$ are the minimal models of P . As neither program contains any negation as failure, this means that $AS(P_{unsat(a,b)}) = AS(P)$.

□

Theorem 4.3. Let S be a CDL specification, let *Assignments* be a set of pairs $\langle e_1, e_2 \rangle$, where e_1 and e_2 are both variable free values occurring in S and let \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} be new atoms.

1. $(\Pi_S)_{unsat(a,b)} \cup \{\mathcal{M}_{translation}(\mathbf{e}_1 = \mathbf{e}_2) \mid \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \in \text{Assignments}\} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\} \models_b \mathbf{a}$ iff there is no extension of the CDL-interpretation $\{(\mathbf{e}_1 = \mathbf{e}_2 \mid \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \in \text{Assignments})\}$ that is a CDL-model of S .

2. $(\Pi_S)_{\text{unsat}(a,b)} \cup \{\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(\mathbf{e}_1 = \mathbf{e}_2) \mid \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \in \text{Assignments}\}$ has at least one answer set that does not contain **a** iff there is an extension of the CDL-interpretation $\{\langle \mathbf{e}_1 = \mathbf{e}_2 \mid \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \in \text{Assignments}\}$ that is a CDL-model of S .

Proof.

1. Assume $(\Pi_S)_{\text{unsat}(a,b)} \cup \{\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(\mathbf{e}_1 = \mathbf{e}_2) \mid \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \in \text{Assignments}\} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\} \models_b \mathbf{a}$.
 $\Leftrightarrow (\Pi_{S'})_{\text{unsat}(a,b)} \cup \{\mathbf{b}\} \models_b \mathbf{a}$, where $S' = S \cup \{\mathbf{e}_1 = \mathbf{e}_2 \mid \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \in \text{Assignments}\}$ (as the two programs are the same).
 $\Leftrightarrow \Pi_{S'} \models_c \mathbf{a}$ (by Lemma 4.2).
 $\Leftrightarrow S'$ has no CDL-models (by Theorem 4.1).
 $\Leftrightarrow S$ has no CDL-models that extend $\{\langle \mathbf{e}_1 = \mathbf{e}_2 \mid \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \in \text{Assignments}\}$.
2. Assume $(\Pi_S)_{\text{unsat}(a,b)} \cup \{\mathcal{M}_{\text{translation}}(\mathbf{e}_1 = \mathbf{e}_2) \mid \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \in \text{Assignments}\}$ has an answer set that does not contain **a**.
 $\Leftrightarrow (\Pi_{S'})_{\text{unsat}(a,b)}$ has an answer set that does not contain **a**, where $S' = S \cup \{\mathbf{e}_1 = \mathbf{e}_2 \mid \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \in \text{Assignments}\}$ (as the two programs are the same).
 $\Leftrightarrow \Pi_{S'}$ has an answer set that does not contain **a** (by Lemma 4.2).
 $\Leftrightarrow S'$ has a CDL-model (by Theorem 4.1).
 $\Leftrightarrow S$ has a CDL-model that extends $\{\langle \mathbf{e}_1 = \mathbf{e}_2 \mid \langle e_1, e_2 \rangle \in \text{Assignments}\}$.

□

4.3 Representing Timelines in the CDL

Definition 4.5. Let S be a set of CDL-statements and t be a ground term. Π_S^t is the program constructed by taking Π_S and adding t as an extra (final) argument to every atom in the program.

By taking the union of many Π_S^t 's for different constants \mathbf{t} , a single answer set can be used to represent many CDL-interpretations. In order to link the various interpretations, we use the general program Π^{temporal} .

Definition 4.6. Π^{temporal} is the program containing the following components, for each $t \in TP$:

- For each $t \in TP$, the rule $\text{holds}(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{t}) :- \text{holds}(\text{fn}(\mathbf{t}, \text{satisfies}, \mathbf{C})), \text{base}$.
- For each $t \in TP$, the rule $\text{consistent}(\mathbf{t}) :- \text{holds}(\text{fn}(\mathbf{t}, \text{consistent})), \text{base}$.
- For each $t \in TP$, the rule $\text{inc}(\mathbf{t}) :- \text{holds}(\text{fn}(\mathbf{t}, \text{inconsistent})), \text{base}$.
- For each $t \in TP$, the rule $\text{eq}(\mathbf{E1}, \mathbf{E2}, \mathbf{t}) :- \text{eq}(\mathbf{E1}, \mathbf{E2}, \text{base})$.
- For each $t \in TP$, the rule $\text{eq}(\mathbf{E1}, \mathbf{E2}, \text{base}) :- \text{eq}(\mathbf{E1}, \mathbf{E2}, \mathbf{t}), \text{consistent}(\mathbf{t})$.
- The constraint $:- \text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\perp), \mathbf{T}), \text{consistent}(\mathbf{T})$.
- The constraint $:- \text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\perp), \text{base})$.

- The rule $\text{model} :- \text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\perp), T) : \text{inc}(T)$.

Definition 4.7. Let S be a set of CDL statements with the time points TPs . Π_S^{temporal} is the program containing the following components:

- Π_S^{base}
- $\Pi_{\text{unsat}(\text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\perp), t), \text{inc}(t))}^t$ for each $t \in TP$
- Π^{temporal} .

Theorem 4.4. Let S be a set of CDL statements. $\Pi_S^{\text{temporal}} \models_b \text{model}$ if and only if S has at least one temporal CDL-model.

The proof of this Theorem follows from Theorem 4.3 (each program $\Pi_{\text{unsat}(\text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\perp), t), \text{inc}(t))}^t$ is isomorphic to $\Pi_{\text{unsat}(\text{holds}(\mathcal{M}_{\text{term}}(\perp), t), \text{inc}(t))}$) and the fact that the rules in Π^{temporal} are a direct translation of the definition of a CDL-temporal model.

5 Verification Mode

First, consider an obvious corollary of the splitting set theorem [LT94].

Corollary 5.1. Let P and C_1, \dots, C_n be ASP programs and let a_1, \dots, a_n be a set of (distinct) atoms that do not occur in any of the ASP programs. Consider the program P' comprising the following:

- P
- $\text{head} :- \text{body}, a_i$ for each rule $\text{head} :- \text{body}$ in C_i
- The choice rule $1\{a_1, \dots, a_n\}1$.

$$AS(P) = \{A \cup \{a_i\} \mid i \in [1, n], A \in AS(P \cup C_i)\}.$$

Definition 5.1. Let S be a CDL-specification and let $\text{Incs} = \{\text{Inc}_1, \dots, \text{Inc}_n\}$ be a set of inconsistency specifications. Π_S^{Incs} is the program consisting of:

- Π_S^{temporal}
- $\text{head} :- \text{body}, \text{inc}(\text{Inc}_i^{\text{id}})$ for each rule $\text{head} :- \text{body}$ in $\Pi_{\text{INC}_i}^{\text{temporal}}$ (where each Inc_i^{id} is a unique identifier for Inc_i)
- The choice rule $1\{a_1, \dots, a_n\}1$.

When the VT is invoked, it is given as input a CDL specification S and a set of inconsistency specifications Incs . It finds the set of inconsistency specifications $\text{Inc} \in \text{Incs}$ such that $\Pi_S^{\text{Incs}} \cup \{:- \text{not model} \models_b \text{inc}(\text{Inc}^{\text{id}})\}$ and reports this set of inconsistencies. We can now prove the soundness and completeness of the verification mode of the tool w.r.t. the set of inconsistency specifications it reports. We say that it is *sound* if every inconsistency specification it reports is violated by S and *complete* if every violated inconsistency specification in Incs is reported by the tool. Both properties are guaranteed by the following theorem.

Theorem 5.2. *Let S be a CDL-specification and let $Inc_s = \{Inc_1, \dots, Inc_n\}$. Let V be the set of inconsistency identifiers returned by the verification mode of the VT when it is invoked on S and Inc_s . For any $Inc \in Inc_s$, $Inc \in V$ if and only if V is violated by S .*

Proof. Let $Inc \in Inc_s$ and assume that $Inc \in V$. This is the case if and only if $\Pi_S^{Inc_s} \models_b \text{inc}(Inc^{id}) \wedge \text{model}$. By Corollary 5.1, this holds if and only if $\Pi_S \cup \Pi_{Inc} \models_b \text{model}$. By Theorem 4.4, this is true if and only if Inc is violated by S . \square

6 Correction Mode

When the VT is run in correction mode, it follows an iterative process, flipping between finding an inconsistency instance for the current model (using the VT's verification mode) and a correction phase, which searches for a correction to the model which does not have any of the inconsistency instances found so far. The verification mode was detailed in the previous section. The correction phase transforms each of the inconsistency instances found so far into examples for the ILASP system. Each example rules out not only the current model, but other models that share similar inconsistency instances. This relies on the following two lemmas.

We now formally define the learning task used by the correction phase of the algorithm. After n iterations, the algorithm has built up a set of n answer sets $\{I_1, \dots, I_n\}$. In each iteration i , the iteration I_i is added to the set, where I_i is an answer set of $\Pi_{S_i}^{Inc_s}$ where S_i is the current CDL specification. The CDL specification S_1 is the initial (uncorrected) CDL specification. The goal of the correction phase is to find a corrected CDL specification S_{i+1} with none of the inconsistency instances found so far. In order to do so, we represent each I_i as an ILASP example.

Definition 6.1. Let S_i be a CDL specification, I_i be an interpretation and H_s be the set of atoms that occur in at least one disjunctive head in S_i . $e(S_i, I_i)$ is the CDPI $\langle \langle \{\text{false}\} \cup (I_i \cap H_s), \emptyset \rangle, \{\text{false} :- \text{not model}\} \rangle$.

We use ILASP to search for a revision of the program S (where the possible corrections are defined by a space of possible corrections, as described in [Law20]). For simplicity we omit the revision encoding here, but essentially, it is equivalent to searching amongst a space of possible CDL specifications H_1, \dots, H_k for one such that $\mathfrak{f}\Pi_S^{Inc_s}$ ³ satisfies all of the examples constructed so far. The following result shows that all CDL specifications found in previous iterations (i.e. S_1, \dots, S_i) are ruled out by the examples I_1, \dots, I_i .

Theorem 6.1. *For any CDL specification S_i and any answer set $I_i \in AS(\Pi_{S_i}^{Inc_s})$ that contains model , $\mathfrak{f}\Pi_{S_i}^{Inc_s}$ does not accept $e(S_i, I_i)$.*

Proof. Assume for contradiction that $\mathfrak{f}\Pi_{S_i}^{Inc_s}$ accepts $e(S_i, I_i)$. Then, there is an answer set of $\mathfrak{f}\Pi_{S_i}^{Inc_s} \cup \{\text{false} :- \text{not model}\}$ that contains every atom in $I_i \cap H_s$, but does not contain false . Therefore there is an answer set A of $\mathfrak{f}\Pi_{S_i}^{Inc_s}$ that contains $I_i \cap H_s$, contains model and does not contain false . As the program contains no negation as failure, A must be a minimal model of $\mathfrak{f}\Pi_{S_i}^{Inc_s}$, and hence, of $\Pi_{S_i}^{Inc_s}$. As I_i is also a minimal model of $\Pi_{S_i}^{Inc_s}$, and contains an atom model

³For any program P , $\mathfrak{f}P$ denotes the program constructed by replacing the head of every constraint in P with the atom false .

which is not in A , A must contain at least one atom a^* which is not in I . As A is minimal, this implies that there must be a rule $h_1; \dots; h_n :- \text{body}$ in $\Pi_{S_i}^{Incs}$ such that A satisfies the body of the rule, $\text{body} \subseteq (A \cap I_i)$ and $\{h_1, \dots, h_n\} \cap (A \cap I_i)$ is empty (or $(A \cap I_i)$ would be a smaller model of the program). As $\{h_1, \dots, h_n\} \cap I_i$ is non-empty (because I_i satisfies the body of the rule and is a model of the program), n must equal 1 (otherwise $\{h_1, \dots, h_n\} \cap (I_i \cap Hs)$ would be non-empty, and A contains every atom in $(I_i \cap Hs)$). But this is a contradiction, as h_1 cannot be in A , in I_i and not in $(A \cap I)$. Hence, $\mathbb{f} \Pi_{S_i}^{Incs}$ cannot accept $e(S_i, I_i)$. \square

The following result shows that the examples only rule out CDL specifications that are not solutions of the correction task.

Theorem 6.2. *For any CDL specification S_i and any answer set $I_i \in AS(\Pi_{S_i}^{Incs})$. For any CDL specification S , if $\mathbb{f} \Pi_S^{Incs}$ does not accept $e(S_i, I_i)$, then at least one $Inc \in Incs$ is violated by S .*

Proof. Let S be a CDL specification such that $\mathbb{f} \Pi_S^{Incs}$ does not accept $e(S_i, I_i)$. As $\mathbb{f} \Pi_S^{Incs} \cup e(S_i, I_i)_{ctx}$ is a stratified disjunctive program with no constraints, it must be satisfiable. But it has no answer sets containing `false` (or it would accept the example); hence, it has at least one answer set A that does not contain `false`. A must also contain `model` (or it would contain `false`), and must be an answer set of $\mathbb{f} \Pi_{S_i}^{Incs}$. Hence A is an answer set of $\Pi_{S_i}^{Incs}$ that contains `model`. So, $\Pi_S^{Incs} \models_b \text{model}$. Therefore, at least one $Inc \in Incs$ is violated by S . \square

7 Learning Mode

Definition 7.1. A CDL learning task T is a tuple $\langle B, S_M, E^+, E^- \rangle$, where B is a set of CDL statements, S_M is a set of pairs of the form $\langle cost, s \rangle$, where $cost$ is a positive integer and s is a set of CDL statements, E^+ and E^- are sets of positive examples and negative examples (respectively), each of which is a set of CDL statements. For any subset $S \subseteq S_M$, S is an *inductive solution* of T if and only if each of the following hold:

- $\forall e \in E^+, B \cup S \cup e$ has at least one temporal CDL-model.
- $\forall e \in E^-, B \cup S \cup e$ has no temporal CDL-models.

Furthermore S is an *optimal* inductive solution if there is no other inductive solution with a lower cost.

The verification tool represents CDL learning tasks as ILASP tasks. The formalisation of the task is given in the following definition.

Definition 7.2. Let $T = \langle B, S_M, E^+, E^- \rangle$ be a CDL learning task. T_{LAS} is the ILASP task $\langle \Pi_B^{temporal}, \{ \langle cost, \Pi_s^{temporal} \setminus \Pi^{temporal} \rangle \mid \langle cost, s \rangle \in S_M \}, \{ \langle \langle \{ \text{model}, \emptyset \}, \Pi_s^{temporal} \setminus \Pi^{temporal} \rangle \mid s \in E^+ \}, \{ \langle \langle \{ \text{model}, \emptyset \}, \Pi_s^{temporal} \setminus \Pi^{temporal} \rangle \mid s \in E^- \} \} \rangle$.

Theorem 7.1. *Let $T = \langle B, S_M, E^+, E^- \rangle$ be a CDL learning task. For any subset $S \subseteq S_M$, S is an inductive solution of T if and only if $\Pi_S^{temporal} \setminus \Pi$ is an inductive solution of T_{LAS} .*

Proof. Assume that S is an inductive solution of T .

$\Leftrightarrow S \subseteq S_M, \forall e \in E^+, S \cup e$ has at least one temporal CDL-model, and $\forall e \in E^-, S \cup e$ has no temporal CDL-models (by definition).

$\Leftrightarrow S \subseteq S_M, \forall e \in E^+, \Pi_{BUSUe}^{temporal} \models_b \text{model}$, and $\forall e \in E^-, \Pi_{BUSUe}^{temporal} \not\models_b \text{model}$, by Theorem 4.4).

$\Leftrightarrow S \subseteq S_M, \forall e \in E^+, \Pi_{BUSUe}^{temporal}$ has at least one answer set that extends $\langle \{\text{model}\}, \emptyset \rangle$, and $\forall e \in E^-, \Pi_{BUSUe}^{temporal}$ has no answer set that extends $\langle \{\text{model}\}, \emptyset \rangle$.

$\Leftrightarrow S \subseteq S_M, \forall e \in E^+, \Pi_B^{temporal} \cup (\Pi_S^{temporal} \setminus \Pi^{temporal}) \cup (\Pi_e^{temporal} \setminus \Pi^{temporal})$ has at least one answer set that extends $\langle \{\text{model}\}, \emptyset \rangle$, and $\forall e \in E^-, \Pi_B^{temporal} \cup (\Pi_S^{temporal} \setminus \Pi^{temporal}) \cup (\Pi_e^{temporal} \setminus \Pi^{temporal})$ has no answer set that extends $\langle \{\text{model}\}, \emptyset \rangle$.

$\Leftrightarrow S_{LAS} \subseteq S_M^{LAS}$ (the hypothesis space of T_{LAS}), $\forall e \in E^+, \Pi_B^{temporal} \cup S_{LAS} \cup (\Pi_e^{temporal} \setminus \Pi^{temporal})$ has at least one answer set that extends $\langle \{\text{model}\}, \emptyset \rangle$, and $\forall e \in E^-, \Pi_B^{temporal} \cup S_{LAS} \cup (\Pi_e^{temporal} \setminus \Pi^{temporal})$ has no answer set that extends $\langle \{\text{model}\}, \emptyset \rangle$.

$\Leftrightarrow S_{LAS}$ is an inductive solution of T_{LAS} . □

Corollary 7.2. Let $T = \langle B, S_M, E^+, E^- \rangle$ be a CDL learning task. For any subset $S \subseteq S_M$, S is an optimal inductive solution of T if and only if $\Pi_S^{temporal} \setminus \Pi$ is an optimal inductive solution of T_{LAS} .

8 Conclusion

This document has proven the correctness of the main three modes of the RADON verification tool. For more information on the RADON verification tool, please see the two public deliverables [Law19] and [Law20].

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